

Responding to Children’s (Mathematical) Thinking in Preschool

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With an increasing focus on STEM (DES, 2017) and mathematics education (DES, 2011) in Irish preschool education contexts, this paper reports on the findings of a qualitative study which explored the beliefs and self-reported practices of eight early childhood educators in relation to mathematics in preschool settings. This paper focuses in particular on the answers of participants to questions focusing on educator ‘noticing’: educator recollections of observations of mathematical concepts in children’s free play and their responses to them. Findings show that while participants could recall mathematical aspects of children’s free play or interests, these were not always responded to, or if responded to were responded to in a non-mathematical way. These findings align to those in international research and contribute to the gap in the research context in relation to mathematics in Irish preschool settings.

Introduction

Internationally, recognition of the importance of early childhood education is growing (UNICEF, 2017). This combined with a policy focus on STEM within Irish early childhood education settings (Department of Education and Skills [DES], 2017, 2018a) has led to early childhood STEM practices coming under the spotlight. From a rights-based perspective, young children have a right to mathematics education (Cohrssen & Page, 2016) and to have their mathematical explorations or interests responded to (Dockett & Goff, 2013). However, in order to respond, one first has to notice. Noticing young children’s mathematical explorations recognises not only the mathematical value of the activity, but also children’s competencies in the area of mathematics (Dockett & Goff, 2013). This paper reports on eight early childhood educators’ recognition of and responses to observed mathematical concepts in preschool children’s free play.

Theoretical Framework

Play is considered a key context for young children’s learning that facilitates children’s mathematical explorations as well as providing children with opportunities to problem-solve (Dockett & Gough, 2013; Dooley et al., 2014). Dockett & Goff (2013) contend that while play is a key vehicle for mathematical exploration, children’s engagement with the mathematics can only be valued and enhanced when it is supported by adults in the setting. However, in order to effectively support children’s mathematical explorations and thinking, adults need to have a knowledge of the big ideas of early childhood mathematics (Dooley et al., 2014), recognise the mathematics in children’s play (Dockett & Gough, 2013; Opperman et al., 2016) and be aware of pedagogical strategies to further develop young children’s emerging mathematical ideas (Dooley et al., 2014). Strategies to support young children’s mathematical explorations include mathematical talk and discussion, developing productive

Professional Noticing

According to Ball (2011) “to notice is to observe, realise, or attend to” (p. xx). Noticing effectively is both a complex and challenging professional skill (Jacobs et al., 2010). Dunekacke, et al. (2016) note that the skill of perceiving mathematical situations within the complex, informal environment of a preschool classroom is more challenging, given the emergent nature of the mathematics through child-led play.

Within the context of a play-based approach to early childhood mathematics, Lee (2017) applies this three-part framework to professional noticing of children’s mathematical knowledge and explorations: “noticing mathematical situations in children’s play, interpreting these mathematical episodes and enhancing the mathematical thinking therein” (p. 253).

Dockett & Gough (2013) note that observation is a common tool to document children’s activity in early childhood settings. However, children’s mathematical activity is rarely purposively observed or documented in early childhood practice (Anthony et al., 2015). McCray & Chen (2012) posit that there is a strong link between a preschool teacher’s capability to identify mathematics in play and the quality of mathematical learning in preschool classrooms. Oppermann et al. (2016) contend that being able to recognise and respond to mathematics in children’s play is dependent on the mathematical subject knowledge of the educator. However, mathematics is not often a feature of early childhood training programmes. Lee & Ginsburg (2009) suggest that the traditional focus on other aspects of child development (e.g. social, emotional and language development) in pre-service training courses impacts on educator noticing of mathematical activity. Jacobs et al. (2010) propose that a lack of training in learning to notice aspects of mathematics in children’s activity in pre-service training contributes to teacher inability to adequately notice children’s mathematical thinking.

Methods

Qualitative semi-structured interviews were employed in this study as they provide a flexible method of gaining insight into participants’ views on a topic and allow participants to expand on issues that are significant and meaningful to them (Bryman, 2016). Semi-structured interviews were chosen over questionnaire survey data collection methods, as it was thought that questionnaires would provide insufficient detail about beliefs and practices or reveal only limited aspects of participants’ thinking (Walliman, 2014) about mathematical activity in preschool.

Research Sample

The data reported in this paper is drawn from a study which explored the beliefs and self-reported practices of eight Irish preschool educators in relation to mathematics. The eight participants varied in level of qualification from those completing a level 6 qualification in Montessori teaching to those with an honours Bachelor degree in Early Childhood Care and Education. Length of experience varied from new entrant (student) to twenty-five years.

Pseudonyms were applied and ethical procedures were followed in accordance with ethical research guidelines issued by NUI Galway.

Findings

This paper focuses on the analysis of the answers of participants to the questions: can you recall some play scenarios in which you observed children's developing mathematical concepts and how did you interact with the child(ren)? Interview transcripts were analysed against Lee's (2017) three constructs of preschool educator professional noticing for mathematics: Noticing, Interpreting and Enhancing.

Louise recalled for 'Show and Tell' a child brought in a measuring tape and "measured everyone in the room...seeing who was the tallest and smallest...that was lovely...we weren't aware it had any sort of mathematical links to it...it was about understanding that everybody's different...we focussed more on accepting everyone for who they are, rather on different heights". Defending her interpretation, Louise stated, "I'm more socially minded so I focus on your feelings and your emotions and your perception of other people".

While Louise did not enhance it mathematically at the time, during the interview, she offered ways in which she could have developed the activity in a mathematical way. "I might have had height charts or something and matched the heights...gotten the children to measure themselves".

Louise also recollected an observation of children building houses with blocks, "they were talking about the shape of the windows and the height of the chimney...one was saying 'my chimney's very tall and your chimney's very small". Louise acknowledged that she didn't recognise the mathematics in that play episode, stating "I was putting it down as them communicating and exploring the world around them...I didn't see or think about the mathematical underpinning of it...until now".

Eileen remembered a play scenario where two children playing with a set of connecting blocks. "They said they were going to see how far it was to the moon and were using their 'rope' to measure the distance". Eileen added, "they were thinking about measuring, but in a way that meant something to them...I wish I had a book on Space to extend it, we could have looked at planets". Eileen had acknowledged that the children were engaged in measuring but interpreted the children's interest as being in 'Space' and not measuring, despite the children having, "repeated the activity a few times". Space would be the focus of enhancement.

Ann noticed two children hanging clothes on a washing line, "the conversation was about the amount of pegs and if there was going to be enough to hang all the clothes...there wasn't and they went back along the line and shared the pegs between the clothes so there would be enough". Ann interpreted the scenario as the children being involved in 'estimating, will there be enough pegs and I suppose sharing is dividing?' Ann also stated, "they were definitely problem-solving". However, no enhancement activity took place as Ann decided

that as the children had, “worked it out by themselves”, no support or enhancement was necessary on her part.

Other participants also took the view that if children were playing mathematically, there was no need for adult enhancement. Carol, noted that her role was that of facilitator of a rich environment, where children were “let to learn it themselves”. This sentiment was echoed by two Montessori participants, who valued the mathematical aspects of the Montessori sensorial materials and children’s self-discovery of these.

Aisling, recalled an observation of children making a car park with construction materials, where some boys were involved in “measuring space for cars and comparing the size of spaces and toy cars, then some girls joined in and the car park became a house with bedrooms...lovely teamwork”. When asked how she responded to this observation, Aisling said “there was no need, they were so happy and playing well together”.

Discussion

Participants could recall episodes of children’s play where mathematical concepts were a feature. This suggests that, at some level, educators are noticing mathematical language or interests in children’s play. However, in the case of Louise, noticing was done retrospectively during the interview process. She also considered ways to develop the mathematical thinking during the interview. Perhaps this indicates that mentor support can help educators to reflect on their observations of play episodes in a mathematical way? At present, such support is facilitated by the DES early years inspectorate (DES, 2017). While this support is welcome, few inspectors are currently employed in this role (DES, 2018b) so it may be some time before early years educators can avail of this much needed support.

While this is a small-scale study, it seems likely that some educators are still predominantly biased towards a focus on developing children’s social and emotional development. This is evident in Louise’s response where she clearly states that, “I’m more socially minded so I focus on your feelings and your emotions and your perception of other people”. This outlook is well-documented in the research literature (e.g. Lee & Ginsburg, 2009) and is often attributed to the assumption that mathematics in preschool is not appropriate (Lee & Ginsburg, 2009) or indeed valued (Hachey, 2013).

The finding that educators do not respond to mathematics observed in children’s play is problematic. Young children are not having their mathematical explorations/interests validated. This goes against the rights based perspective argued by Cohrssen & Page (2016) who express the ‘ethical obligation’ of educators to prepare children for life by supporting their mathematical development (p. 104). How can educators be meeting this obligation when they are not responding to the mathematics observed? Perhaps it is a question of educators not recognising this right, or perhaps, there is a tension between the importance of mathematics and the goals for social development (Lee & Ginsburg, 2009)?

This paper suggests that there is also a need to argue against the role of the educator solely as a facilitator of a mathematically rich environment, (e.g. Carol and Montessori

participants) where children's mathematical ideas are self-discovered and supported by their interactions with objects in the environment. Educators need to understand the importance of their role in supporting mathematical development through interactions, through strategies such as mathematical talk and discussion, development of productive disposition, mathematical modelling, providing cognitively challenging tasks (enhancing) and engaging in formative assessment (Dooley et al., 2014).

Dockett & Gough (2013) note that in order to notice and respond to children's mathematical explorations, educators need a solid understanding of mathematics. At present, modules in mathematics /STEM education are not mandatory for pre-service early childhood education in Ireland (DES, 2019) and currently there is no formal continuing professional development in the area. Of the eight participants, only two had attended an undergraduate degree module on literacy and numeracy for early years, however, even with this knowledge, Eileen chose to focus on enhancing children's interest in Space rather than on children's explorations of measure.

This paper contributes an Irish perspective to international literature on mathematics in preschool classrooms. Findings align with well-established conclusions on educator attitudes towards mathematics in preschool. Further studies are needed to explore why, even when armed with training in early years mathematics, Irish early childhood educators choose not to focus on enhancing the mathematics observed in children's play.

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